

Natural Frequency and Damping Properties of Composite Sandwich Materials Manufactured using Vacuum-Assisted Resin Infusion, Vacuum Bagging, and Hand Lay-Up

Nur Mufidatul Ula¹, Nurul Lailatul Muzayadah¹, Muksin¹, Mikhael Gilang Pribadi Putra Pratama^{1,*}, Yusuf Giri Wijaya¹, Afid Nugroho^{1,*}

¹Research Centre for Aeronautics Technology, National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), Bogor 16350, Indonesia

*Author to whom correspondence should be addressed:
E-mail: mikh001@brin.go.id (MGPPP); afid001@brin.go.id (AN)

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Abstract: Vibration testing was conducted on composite sandwich structures manufactured using different fabrication techniques, including vacuum-assisted resin infusion, vacuum bagging, and hand lay-up. Two carbon fiber orientations—twill and unidirectional—were evaluated, with each classification further analyzed in three-layer configurations: 2C2, 3C3, and 4C2. Vinyl ester resin was employed as the matrix, while Divinycell foam served as the core material. Experimental results indicated that structures with unidirectional fibers exhibited higher fundamental frequencies compared to those with twill fibers. Among the manufacturing techniques, vacuum-assisted resin infusion produced composites with the highest natural frequency across all sample variations. The damping ratio values showed significant variability, with the 3C3 configuration demonstrating a reduced damping ratio compared to other sample variations across fiber types and manufacturing methods. Further research is required to investigate discrepancies in sample behavior, fabrication methodologies, and evaluation techniques.

Keywords: damping properties; hand lay-up; sandwich composite material; vacuum assisted resin infusion; vacuum bagging

1. Introduction

The development of energy-efficient technologies is advancing rapidly, particularly in the aerospace sector, where improving fuel efficiency is a critical objective. A key strategy for enhancing energy efficiency in aviation is reducing aircraft weight, which lowers fuel consumption and increases payload capacity. Lightweight composite materials play a pivotal role in achieving these goals, driving ongoing research into innovative manufacturing techniques and material optimization. A material that has developed to meet these property criteria and holds promise in numerous applications is composite materials¹. Composites are widely used in the fabrication of lightweight structures, particularly in aerospace and automotive industries, due to their high specific strength, failure strain, and specific stiffness²⁻⁵. The mechanical properties of composite materials are highly influenced by their design, including factors such as fiber type, resin-to-fiber ratio, fiber orientation, and the manufacturing process used in their production. A comparative study by Abdurrahman et al. and Talabari et al. investigated

manufacturing methods such as vacuum infusion, hand lay-up, and vacuum bagging. Their findings indicate that vacuum infusion is the most efficient technique, as it ensures superior bonding within the matrix and adhesive, resulting in enhanced mechanical properties^{6,7}. Rajeshkumar et al. demonstrated in previous studies that the manufacturing method plays a critical role in determining the vibrational characteristics of composite materials⁸. The manufacturing method significantly influences the fiber volume fraction, which affects composites' mechanical performance. Liu et al. demonstrated a notable correlation between fiber volume fraction and the vibrational characteristics of composite materials⁹.

Structural stability is essential in engineering systems to ensure durability and prevent damage caused by external vibrations¹⁰. In the aerospace sector, there has been a growing shift toward the use of fiber-reinforced plastic materials, replacing stainless steel and similar materials. This transition is driven by their advantageous properties, including superior corrosion resistance, low thermal expansion, and excellent damping capabilities^{11,12}. The

dynamic characteristics of composite laminates made from glass fiber and epoxy resin have been investigated.^{13,14}. Furthermore, another study reveals that combining brittle fibers with high-performance fibers, specifically Kevlar and S-glass, with epoxy resin significantly improves damping capacitance¹⁵. Qing Li and Deqing conducted a study on the vibrational characteristics of composite structures with Auxetic Double Arrowed Honeycomb (DAH) cores, discovering improvements in vibroacoustic and bending performance over conventional hexagonal honeycomb cores¹⁶.

Natural frequency, damping ratio, and absorbent mass are crucial factors for structural design engineers focused on ensuring comfort and vibration safety¹⁷. This study focused on determining one of the key parameters, specifically the damping properties, using frequency domain data. Numerous studies have shown that frequency domain data provides superior results for non-uniform materials, such as composites^{6,18}. Several prior studies have indicated that the damping characteristics of carbon fiber composites are generally inferior to those of alternative fibers¹⁹.

Research on the mechanical properties of composites produced through various manufacturing methods has been extensive; however, there remains a gap in data regarding their dynamic properties. The findings from this dynamic characteristic data will contribute to a refined database for optimizing composite manufacturing techniques, particularly for applications requiring specific dynamic performance, such as those in the automotive and aerospace industries. This study offers valuable insights into the effects of different production methods on composites' frequency and damping characteristics during vibration testing. It also introduces a novel approach for assessing the dynamic characteristics of composite sandwich structures using a modal shaker and a contact-type accelerometer. This method has been infrequently utilized. In this investigation, half-power bandwidth was employed to analyze each sample variation's natural frequency and damping characteristics. The study aimed to evaluate the dynamic properties of various sandwich composites made from carbon fiber with two fiber orientations: Twill (0°/90°) and Unidirectional (0°).

2. Methodology

2.1. Materials and Manufacturing Process

The materials used in this investigation included Carbon Unidirectional (UD) 12 K Tow (Torayca UT70-20G, fiber weight 200 gr/m², density 1.8 gr/cm³, tensile strength 3.4 kN/mm², Young's modulus 230 kN/mm²) sourced from Toray Industries, Inc., as well as Carbon Twill 3 K Tow (fiber carbon HDC-524-3K, tensile modulus 230 GPa, fiber weight 220 gr/m²) obtained from PT. Justus Kimiaraya. The study utilized Unidirectional fibers at 0°

and 0°/90° Twill fibers. Vinyl-Ester resin (Ripoxy R-800-EX (VI), with a viscosity of 0.9 – 2.3 poise at 25°C and a gel time of 45 - 65 minutes at 25°C) was employed as the matrix. The curing process of the vinyl ester resin was enhanced using cobalt solution P-EX and cumene hydroperoxide solution Percumyl-H, which served as effective promoters and catalysts, with the formulation Resin, Promotor P-EX, and Percumyl-H in a 100:0.4:1 ratio. The core of the composite structures consisted of Divinycell foam (H80 Grade, density 80 kg/m³, compressive strength 1.4 MPa, compressive modulus 90 MPa, tensile strength 2.5 MPa, tensile modulus 95 MPa) with a thickness of 6 mm. The resin, promoter, catalyst, and core foam materials were supplied by PT. Justus Kimiaraya. The configuration of the test specimen is illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1: The Setup of Test Specimens

Method	Reinforcement	Configuration	Mass (gr)	Thickness (mm)
Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion	Carbon UD 12K	2C2	40.62	8
		3C3	52.92	8.57
		4C2	52.62	8.86
	Carbon Twill 3K	2C2	32.55	7.35
		3C3	37.18	7.75
		4C2	42.17	7.95
Vacuum Bagging	Carbon UD 12K	2C2	26	6.9
		3C3	34	7.3
		4C2	34.6	7.4
	Carbon Twill 3K	2C2	22	6.6
		3C3	30	7.0
		4C2	29	7.1
Hand Lay-Up	Carbon UD 12K	2C2	41	7.8
		3C3	52	8.7
		4C2	52.62	8.9
	Carbon Twill 3K	2C2	36	7.2
		3C3	52	8.0
		4C2	44	7.8

The composite specimens were fabricated with a 1:1 resin-to-fiber mass ratio, with no ratio applied to the core material. While this ratio was used during initial manufacturing, the final composite ratios will require recalculation. A total of 18 specimens were produced using three manufacturing methods and two fiber types: twill and unidirectional. The layer configuration of each specimen was denoted by two numbers and one letter, where the numbers represented the fiber layers and "C" indicated the core. Figure 1 illustrates the layer configurations²⁰. All specimens had dimensions of 230 mm in length and 50 mm in width, varying thickness according to the number of layers.

Fig. 1: Configuration of material test samples²⁰⁾

In this research, composite sandwich structures were fabricated using three manufacturing processes: Vacuum-Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI), Vacuum Bagging (VB), and Hand Lay-up (HLU). Figure 2 illustrates the setup differences between these methods. The VARI process was conducted under a vacuum pressure of -100 kPa and is widely recognized for its advantages in producing lightweight composites. These advantages include its cost-effectiveness, ability to manufacture large and complex components, and proficiency in minimizing void content²¹⁾. However, it required disposable auxiliary materials, such as sealing tape, peel ply, and release agents²²⁾. On the other hand, the VB technique offered simpler manufacturing and the ability to create complex geometries and large, high-quality composites. Nevertheless, it generated more voids and required more disposable materials than VARI^{6,23)}. In contrast, the HLU method was the most straightforward process but exhibited significant drawbacks, including high void content and weaker bonding between the matrix and resin due to its reliance on operator skill^{6,24)}.

Fig. 2: The illustration of the manufacturing set-up of (a) VB, (b) HLU, and (c) VARI

The composite plates fabricated using the three manufacturing processes had 10×25 cm dimensions. The gel time for the composites was approximately 25 minutes. After fabrication, all specimens were cured at room temperature (25°C) for 24 hours without post-curing treatment.

2.2. Experimental Setup

The study involved the collection of vibration data from composite specimens using the Oberst beam method. This traditional technique employs a multilayer cantilever beam consisting of a base beam and one or two additional layers made of different materials²⁵⁾. During data collection, the composite sample was subjected to vibration at the center, exhibiting dynamic properties characteristic of a half-cantilever beam²⁶⁻²⁸⁾. Cyanoacrylate ethyl glue was used to attach the composite specimens to the fixture, while accelerometer adhesive (Petro wax) was employed to secure the accelerometer sensors. The fixture connected the modal shaker to the composite specimen, which was constructed from aluminum.

Two SENZ accelerometers (type 3055B2) were used in this study. The first accelerometer was used to give feedback on the shaker controller. It was mounted on the fixture, while the second accelerometer measured the vibration response signals and was positioned on the composite specimen. A single sensor position was selected for vibration response measurement, arbitrarily placed 9 cm from the specimen's center to facilitate sensor placement (Figure 3). The vibration test setup included a Bruel & Kjaer modal shaker (type 4809) and an amplifier (type 2706). Figure 4 provides an overview of the instrumentation configuration used during testing.

Fig. 3: Specimen and sensor position in vibration testing tool

Fig. 4: Instrumentation configuration for data collection

The frequency sweep on the test sample began at 10 Hz and extended to 2000 Hz, with an excitation level of 1 g and a sweep rate of 0.25 octave/minute. This sweep rate was selected based on prior test results, as it effectively shapes the resonance peak at low frequencies and ensures reliable comparisons between different systems²⁶. Previous findings indicated that a sweep rate below 0.5 octave/minute was optimal, necessitating adjustments to existing references. Each composite sample underwent the sine sweep test three times to ensure accuracy and repeatability. The analysis focused on extracting the primary dynamic characteristics of the samples, specifically their natural frequencies and damping properties.

3. Result And Discussion

Vibration testing was conducted on 18 sandwich composite samples, and the resulting natural frequencies were presented in Figure 5. The composites fabricated with unidirectional fibers exhibited higher natural frequencies compared to those made with twill fibers. These findings align with the study by Xiao Yuan Pei et al., which demonstrated that fiber alignment significantly influences the natural frequency of composite structures. The findings suggest that an increase in fiber orientation angle is associated with a reduction in natural frequency²⁹.

Fig. 5: Natural frequencies of samples from three different manufacturing processes with two fiber direction types

The analysis of two fiber types combined with three different manufacturing techniques revealed that the VARI method consistently produced the highest natural frequency across all 2C2, 3C3, and 4C2 sample variations. This outcome could be attributed to the superior stiffness of composites fabricated using the VARI method, which

resulted in enhanced natural frequency compared to those produced by vacuum bagging and hand lay-up techniques. This comparison was limited to samples with identical compositions. One potential factor influencing composite stiffness was the amount of resin absorbed during fabrication. Previous studies have demonstrated that resin absorption levels directly impact void content, mechanical properties, and overall stiffness, suggesting that variations in resin distribution may contribute to the observed differences in natural frequency^{30,31}. The stiffness and void content of the composite also influence the resulting damping values. Among the manufacturing techniques, hand lay-up posed a higher risk of introducing variability in resin content, which could lead to slight discrepancies in test outcomes. In contrast, the VARI method regulated resin infusion through controlled pressure, ensuring a consistent resin distribution and minimizing variations in composite properties.

The damping properties, as illustrated in Figure 6, indicate that the damping ratio of sample 3C3 was lower than that of the other two configurations in both the twill and unidirectional fiber orientations. The fiber arrangement, particularly the number of laminae in the laminate, significantly influenced the damping ratio. Sample 4C2 exhibited a higher damping ratio than sample 3C3 in both fiber orientations, which can be attributed to differences in stiffness between the top and bottom faces of the sandwich structure. These stiffness variations resulted in differing deflection amplitudes when subjected to vibrations in both upward and downward directions. This discrepancy in deflection amplitude affected strain energy dissipation, where the less rigid side exhibited greater energy dissipation. Since strain energy dissipation is directly correlated with damping performance, the higher damping ratio observed in sample 4C2 was expected. Additionally, variations in damping ratio values could be influenced by sensor placement on the test sample and the thickness of the adhesive used, introducing minor inconsistencies in measurement.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6: The damping ratio of samples from three different manufacturing processes) twill fibers (b) UD fibers

Previous studies have shown that the hand lay-up technique produces the highest void content, followed by the vacuum bagging method. In contrast, the vacuum-assisted resin infusion (VARI) method results in the lowest void occurrence. This trend directly influenced the natural frequency of composites, as reduced void content enhances stiffness, leading to higher natural frequencies. Another critical factor affecting natural frequency was the fiber volume fraction (Vf). A higher Vf generally indicates increased stiffness, which, in turn, raises the natural frequency. However, as illustrated in Figure 7, the findings of this study suggested that variations in fiber orientation have a more pronounced impact on the stiffness of sandwich composites than fiber volume fraction.

Fig. 7: Data on the natural frequency of each sample in relation to fiber volume fraction

The data visualization presented in this study provides a preliminary reference for selecting materials with desirable damping properties. However, it should not be considered a definitive reference due to its foundational nature. While the trend suggested that the damping properties in variations up to 3C3 were lower than those of other sample configurations, this does not preclude the selection of materials based solely on damping performance. A more comprehensive evaluation is necessary, focusing on key variables related to mechanical properties to ensure an informed selection of structural materials. The outcomes included evaluations such as compressive strength, three-

point bending tests, tensile tests, and impact tests, all of which were analyzed in relation to both the laminate components and the sandwich configuration. A specific proposition indicates that the laminates within the sandwich composite play a role in distributing loads generated by flexural and compression forces, whereas the core is responsible for managing the load caused by shearing³².

Further investigation is needed to fully understand the impact of the manufacturing method on dynamic characteristics. Additional data collection across various fiber types and resins is essential for a more comprehensive comparison. This expanded dataset would enhance the structural design process. Additionally, the mass of the sensor should be considered when interpreting the collected data. Future studies should explore using non-contact sensors to improve measurement accuracy and reduce potential sensor-induced errors.

4. Conclusions

The analysis of the natural frequency values and damping characteristics from 18 samples revealed that the natural frequency values of the Vacuum Resin Infusion samples surpassed those of the other two manufacturing methods in all variations of the test samples. The findings from this test indicate that the VARI sample exhibits a greater stiffness value than the other samples, corresponding with a reduction in void occurrence. The orientation of the fibers has a considerable impact on the value of the natural frequency. The uni-directional fiber orientation demonstrates a higher natural frequency value than the composite incorporating twill fiber. The values of the damping properties across the three manufacturing types show considerable differences. The variation of the 3C3 sample across two fiber types and three manufacturing methods demonstrates a reduced value compared to the variations of other samples. This data could guide the choice of specific materials for comparison with the tested samples. However, this should not be seen as a definitive reference, as it is crucial to consider other variables and variations within the sample. Future investigations should focus on replicating data collection with similar materials to confirm data trends. Additional investigations ought to include the application of non-contact sensors.

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